

WEB PAGE CLASSIFICATION USING UNSUPERVISED AND SEMI-SUPERVISED CLUSTERING TECHNIQUES

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Abstract

In light of ever increasing amounts of data, the efficient and robust search and retrieval of information from different open and closed data sources is a central task. The quality of search can be improved by metadata extraction and enrichment. Web page classification, i.e., assigning one or more thematic classes to web pages, is a central task in this regard. In this abstract, we address the adaptable and content-based classification of web pages in order to support specific and domain-focused search scenarios.

One example would be to find all relevant documents in a set of news pages reporting about flood events induced by heavy rainfall in a specific area. Since we would like to offer such search capabilities for a wide variety of domains and questions/requests, a flexible concept is required.

A common approach is to use different sets of features including links, neighbours, and contents for supervised classification. Semi-structured information embedded within the web pages such as hyperlinks of interconnected web-pages, other modalities such as images, audio, video etc. can be used to enrich and supplement the information presented by the actual content of web pages.

Different taxonomies for web site classification [1] along with ready-to-use software [2]¹[3]²[4]³[5]⁴ already exist. For instance, it is common practice to utilize web page classifiers for focused crawl campaigns [6]. A plethora of existing methods use supervised techniques based on various features of the web pages for classification [1]. However, existing taxonomies tend to represent rather general and static classes, like entertainment, sports, people, travel etc. [7]. Additionally, pre-trained models tend to be insufficient for searching domain-specific content, as an alternative categorization with more fine-grained thematic classes may be desired. This poses a challenge, when the labels of the web pages to be classified are not a priori available. Motivated by this, we focus on unsupervised approaches for web page classification.

Unsupervised web classification methods using URL based features [8], content based features such as Multi-purpose Internet Mail Extensions (MIME) content breakdown [9] and external subdomain connection have shown promising results with regards to processing speed, scalability [8] and Quality of Experience (QoE) perceived by the user-groups [9].

In this study, we outline our specific approach to web page classification. The core idea here is to offer flexibility in terms of topics, domains as well as granularity. Based on this, we propose a first concept, which involves unsupervised and semi-supervised clustering, and investigates the usefulness of URL-based, content based and other web page features to achieve general yet highly adaptable categorization of web page categories.

Finally, initial results from experiments using the proposed concept are presented and discussed. The evaluation of experiments will be carried out on data collected using the Owler crawler⁵, and lastly, alleys for future work are pointed out.

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¹ <https://www.whoisxmlapi.com/>

² <https://www.cyren.com/security-center/url-category-check>

³ <https://developers.similarweb.com/docs/similarweb-web-traffic-api>

⁴ <https://www.safedns.com/>

⁵ <https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/owlr>